

Hydrogen Uptake by Porphyrins at the TiO₂(110) Surface.

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ABSTRACT. We show by core level x-ray photoemission that metal-free porphyrin molecules are able to capture two hydrogen atoms from the rutile TiO₂(110) surface. Theoretical simulations of the corresponding N 1s core level shift and of the molecular topography for the case of 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin show that molecules adsorb with their pristine pyrrolic nitrogen atoms atop the O-bridge rows, whereas two additional hydrogen atoms bond to the iminic nitrogen atoms. The hydrogenation process occurs at room temperature, irrespective of the distance of the polypyrrolic macrocycle from the surface, as is verified by changing the porphyrin functionalization.

Metal porphyrins (MPs) and phthalocyanines (MPcs) offer a large variety of electronic configurations that, when brought into contact with a substrate, can display the most diverse electronic and chemical functionalities,¹ spanning from magnetism²⁻⁴ to catalysis.⁵⁻⁷ In this context, the metal-free molecular homologues (2H-P and 2H-Pc) display a large flexibility, as they can be suitably metalated in situ by post growth treatment, either by metal extraction from the substrate,⁸⁻¹² or by incorporation of diffusing adatoms (e.g. after atomic beam deposition).¹³⁻¹⁵ Hydrogen itself can be exploited to modify the local molecular conductance by selective cleavage of one pyrrolic NH bond in 2H-P,¹⁶ as well as to tune the chirality by selective adsorption in MnPc.¹⁷

In order to generalize these functionalities, one must keep into account the nature of the substrate, which is demonstrated to affect the gas reactivity of the MP contact layer.⁷ The interface of titania with MPs and MPcs attracts large interest because of its dual purpose applications in photocatalysis and solar cells. In particular, the rutile TiO₂(110) surface is a suitable template for the growth of poly- and hetero-aromatic molecules thanks to its large and anisotropic surface corrugation. Phthalocyanine and porphyrin films are expected to grow with the molecular macrocycles closely parallel to the substrate,^{15,18,19} a geometry that favors intermolecular charge transport²⁰ and charge injection into the oxide substrate.²¹

A number of XPS measurements of different phthalocyanines and porphyrins grown on TiO₂(110) has however put in evidence the unexpected presence of pyrrolic nitrogen in metalated species, as well as an excess of pyrrolic nitrogen w.r.t. the iminic one in non-metalated molecules.^{18,22-24} The nature of this component is controversial and has been alternatively attributed to chemical bonding of nitrogen to the oxygen atoms underneath,¹⁸ or to a local surface screening effect,^{22,24} or to hydrogen capture upon molecule de-metalation.²³ To better address this controversial issue we focused on the simplest case of metal-free porphyrins, which contain only two types of nitrogen atoms, namely pyrrolic and iminic. We performed the experiments on three differently functionalized porphyrins: 2H-ter-butyl-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (2H-TBTPP), 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (2H-TTP) and 2H-octa-ethyl-porphyrin (2H-OEP). These different peripheral terminations do not display specific (chemical) affinity to the substrate, and essentially change the height of the central macrocycle w.r.t. the surface by ~1 Å from 2H-TBTPP to 2H-OEP passing through the intermediate 2H-TTP.

The ligand state of nitrogen in 2H-P can be probed by X-ray photoemission (XPS) measurements of the N 1s core level. Metal-free porphyrins are characterized by two well separate N 1s peaks of equal intensity (separation of ~2 eV), corresponding to one pair of hydrogenated (pyrrolic) nitrogen atoms and one pair of iminic (aza) nitrogen atoms.²⁵ However, the first layer molecules always display the occurrence of a dominant component at ~400.2-400.5 eV in the N 1s photoemission spectra, as clearly shown in the bottom curves of Fig. 1 for 2H-TBTPP, 2H-TTP and 2H-OEP (from top to bottom). This binding energy corresponds to that of pyrrolic nitrogen, while the iminic component, which should display the same intensity of the pyrrolic one in presence of regular porphyrins, is residual and is observed to increase only upon condensation of sequent layer molecules at ~398 eV binding energy (see top curves of Fig. 1). We recall that also in metalated species, the four central nitrogen atoms become equivalent, but they yield a binding energy (BE) close to that of the iminic nitrogen atom ($\Delta BE \sim +0.3$ eV), without significant differences among different metal elements.

Figure 1. Comparison between the monolayer (filled blue markers) and multilayer (open black markers) photoemission spectra of the N 1s peak for three different porphyrins ($h\nu = 500$ eV; $\Delta E \sim 160$ meV). All films have been grown with the substrate at room temperature (RT).

Concerning the molecular orientation, the polarization dependent near-edge x-ray absorption spectroscopy (NEXAFS) at the K-edge of nitrogen and carbon always display a large dichroism of the resonances associated with the pyrrolic rings (Supplementary Figs. S1, S2), which indicates that the three molecules are equivalently oriented with the central macrocycle almost parallel to the substrate. The main difference among the adsorption geometries of the molecules is thus the height of the macrocycle above the substrate (2H-TBTPP is ~ 0.5 Å higher than 2H-TPP, which is ~ 0.5 Å higher than 2H-OEP, from simple steric arguments and neglecting minor relaxation effects). This excludes that the absence of the iminic component in the N 1s spectra might be due a strong core level shift (~ 2 - 2.5 eV) of aza-nitrogen, as originated either by a local screening or by a chemical bonding of nitrogen to the oxygen rows underneath. We are then left with the hypothesis of hydrogen uptake, either molecular (from the vacuum residual gas) or atomic (from the substrate). In fact, a large and consolidated body of literature indicates that a significant amount of hydrogen is diluted in the TiO_2 bulk, as favored by thermal treatment, metal (acceptor) contaminants, and electron irradiation.²⁶⁻²⁸ XPS is not a suitable probe of low concentration bulk-diluted species due to its intrinsic surface sensitivity (escape depth of 5-10 Å), however a few percent concentration of surface confined hydrogen species can be obtained by water dissociation at a slightly reduced $\text{TiO}_2(110)$ surface.²⁹ These hydroxyl species

can be easily monitored by photoemission of the valence band where they display the occurrence of a characteristic satellite of the O 2p band at ~ 11 eV.³⁰ In Fig. 2 we compare the valence band spectra of a clean, albeit slightly hydroxylated TiO₂(110) surface (estimated OH concentration of 4-5 %) before and after the deposition of a layer of 2H-TPP, which is the intermediate height molecule. The hydroxyl peak is fully quenched upon molecular deposition in agreement with the hypothesis of hydrogen uptake. We remark that i) full hydrogenation of nitrogen in the first porphyrin layer cannot be fulfilled only by the surface hydroxyls and ii) the nitrogen hydrogenation is observed also in absence of surface hydroxyls. This implies that either hydrogen is captured and dissociated from the residual gas pressure or that the porphyrin macrocycle locally lowers the kinetic barriers which otherwise keep H interstitials in the subsurface region.

Figure 2. Comparison between the extended Valence Band spectra ($h\nu = 140$ eV; $\Delta E \sim 120$ meV) of a slightly hydroxylated TiO₂(110) surface before and after the deposition of 1.0 and 6.5 ML of 2H-TPP. The characteristic photoemission peak of the surface hydroxyls at BE ~ 11 eV is completely quenched upon molecular deposition.

In order to further check the hypothesis of nitrogen hydrogenation, we performed ab initio calculations within the frame of gradient-corrected density functional theory (GGA-DFT) for the intermediate case of 2H-TPP. Grimme’s long-range dispersion corrections were included^{31,32} (see Supplementary Information for details). Calculations predict that the gas-phase hydrogenation of 2H-TPP is slightly exothermic at 0 K (see Table 1), whereas, by assuming an ideal gas behavior for H₂, we can estimate that $\Delta G \approx +0.3$ eV at 298 K. This agrees with the fact that 2H-TPP, and not 4H-TPP, is the species stable at RT in the gas phase. At the same time, it strengthens the possibility that the TiO₂ substrate, which can provide dissociated hydrogen on the surface, favors the stabilization of the 4H-TPP species.

Table 1. Hydrogenation reaction energies

Reaction	ΔG [eV]
$2\text{H-TPP}(\text{gas}) + \text{H}_2(\text{gas}) \rightarrow 4\text{H-TPP}(\text{g})$	-0.10*

*Zero-point energy corrections have been applied.

We then examined the case of adsorbed 2H-TPP, using periodically repeated slab models with PBE-D theoretical lattice constants of the substrate.³³ In order to refine the configuration model of the adsorbed molecule, we performed scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) measurements of a submonolayer coverage of 2H-TPP. As deposited at RT, all the molecules display a preferential adsorption configuration with a common azimuthal orientation. From the analysis of the STM images shown in Fig. 3, we can see that all molecules adsorb atop the oxygen rows with the squared molecular edge parallel to the substrate [001] direction. The individual molecules display a characteristic saddle-shape, which was reported also for 2H-TPP adsorbed on noble metals, and is originated by the opposite upward/downward tilt off the macrocycle plane of adjacent pyrrolic units. The corresponding nodal plane is oriented transverse to the oxygen rows and three distinct lobes can be distinguished on each side.

Figure 3. Left: STM image ($27.5 \times 27.5 \text{ nm}^2$) of $\sim 1/3$ ML of 2H-TPP deposited on the sample at room temperature ($V_s = -1.5 \text{ V}$; $I = 60 \text{ pA}$). The substrate Ti^{5f} (O_{br}) rows along the [001] direction appear as bright (dark) stripes. Right: zoom in of the area indicated by the white square, as displayed with different contrast in order to highlight the molecular adsorption atop the dark O_{br} rows (bottom) and to enhance the intramolecular structure (top).

Because of i) the observed parallel to the surface orientation of the macrocycle (from NEXAFS dichroism) and ii) the D_{2h} symmetric appearance of the molecules, we could limit our tests to two azimuthal orientations: with two opposite nitrogen atoms (N-N axis) oriented either along the substrate [001] direction or at 45° from it (Supplementary Fig. S4). We considered adsorption on both Ti 5-fold coordinated (Ti^{5c}) and oxygen-bridge (O_{br}) rows in both on-top and on-bridge sites (Supplementary Information). The most favored adsorption site for both 2H-TPP and its hydrogenated homologue 4H-TPP is found to be the bridge one between two adjacent O_{br} atoms along [001], with the N-N axis also parallel to the [001] direction. In this configuration, two equivalent $\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}_{\text{br}}$ hydrogen bonds are formed, as depicted in Fig. 4a; this configuration favors the downward tilt of the corresponding pyrrolic rings (Fig. 4b), whose peripheral carbon atoms protrude above the macrocycle plane and yield an enhanced intensity in the topographic images, as shown in the simulation of Fig. 4c. The other two central rings display a tilt in the opposite direction yielding a dimmed contrast in the direction transverse to the O_{br} rows. The

topographic images calculated for 2H-TPP are very similar to those of 4H-TPP, where the main structural difference is found to be the average tilt angle of the pyrrolic rings that increases by 6° upon hydrogen uptake. This difference cannot be appreciated in our STM images (room temperature), but is consistent with the observed dichroism of the residual iminic component in the N *K*-edge NEXAFS, as compared to the pyrrolic one (Supplementary Fig. S2). In this equilibrium configuration, the energy reaction of hydrogen uptake from the surface is much more exothermic (-1.40 eV) with respect to the gas-phase case (Table 1). It is worth noticing that, while the mechanism of hydrogen incorporation into bulk TiO₂ is controversial,^{29,34} there is a general consensus about the interlayer H diffusion barrier calculated to be ~ 1 eV for the TiO₂(110) planes,³⁴ which opens the way also to a possible mechanism of bulk hydrogen uptake.

Figure 4. The ball and stick model of the 4H-TPP adsorption configuration is shown in panel a), where the adopted supercell is also sketched. The simulated STM images is shown in panel b), whose saddle-shape molecular appearance is in excellent agreement with the observed one. The saddle-type deformation of the adsorbate can be also appreciated in the perspective view of panel c) , where the N—H...O_{br} hydrogen bonds are also highlighted as yellow sticks.

DFT simulations of the N1s photoemission peaks were performed using clusters extracted from the previously optimized slab models. These include the adsorbed species as well the relevant part of the first TiO₂ layer, and a convenient number of saturating hydrogen atoms. Results (reported in Table 2) reproduce quite well the observed core level shift (CLS) between the iminic and pyrrolic nitrogen of 2H-TPP. The uptake of two hydrogen atoms is expected to yield a small shift of ~ 0.3 eV towards higher binding energy, BE, w.r.t. the pristine pyrrolic pair (which are coordinated to the oxygen atoms underneath). This is in full agreement with the observed CLS (0.4 eV) and broadening (+50%) of the main pyrrolic component observed in the monolayer range w.r.t. the multilayer one (Supplementary Fig. S3).

Table 2. N 1s binding energy and core level shift w.r.t. pyrrolic N

Molecule	Pyrrolic B.E.	Iminic CLS	Iminic+2H CLS
2H-TPP multilayer	400.15 eV <i>exp</i>	-2.06 eV <i>exp</i>	-
2H-TPP ML	400.55 eV <i>exp</i>	-1.95 eV <i>exp</i>	-

2H-TPP gas	393.30 eV <i>calc</i>	-1.95 eV <i>calc</i>	-
2H-TPP ads	392.78 eV <i>calc</i>	-1.83 eV <i>calc</i>	-
4H-TPP ads	392.73 eV <i>calc</i>	-	+0.32 eV <i>calc</i>

In conclusion, our systematic study of metal-free porphyrins with different functional ends confirms that the TiO₂(110) substrate strongly favors the capture of surface hydrogen by tetrapyrrolic macrocycles, independently of the functional terminations. The energy gain associated with this chemical reaction is found to be larger than the barrier for hydrogen interlayer diffusion, which makes conceivable a hydrogen extraction path from the titania bulk. When comparing our systems with the case of phthalocyanines, one should consider the competitive reaction channel offered by the four additional meso-nitrogen atoms. In fact, upon hydrogen exposure, first layer MnPc molecules on Au(111) have been shown to dissociate and link two hydrogen atoms at opposite meso sites.¹⁷ This reaction path might be enhanced at the TiO₂(110) surface, as observed for the porphyrin case, thus explaining the excess of pyrrolic nitrogen reported also for metalated species like FePc²² and ZnPc.²⁴

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Experimental and computational methods, original NEXAFS data at the K-edge ionization threshold of C and N, XPS fitting analysis of N 1s are included. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>

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Notes

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TOC GRAPHICS

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